

Track Filtering of Boosting Targets

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Abstract – With the shift in focus of the missile defense program from intercept of a ballistic missile during reentry to intercept during ascent, the tracking of ballistic missiles under boost is more important. The paper compares filtering performance using standard approaches to that using compensation from acceleration profiles. The results indicate the acceleration compensation is beneficial when applied to either constant velocity or constant acceleration track filters.

I. INTRODUCTION

Tracking a rocket in boost phase accurately with a multi-purpose radar can be a difficult task: the track filters must be able to handle large values of acceleration at long ranges with high measurement noise conditions. Furthermore, the radar must then be able to gracefully handle the transition from high acceleration boost phase to the low acceleration midcourse phase. One of the difficulties of tracking is trying to match the state prediction model in the filter to the actual rocket kinematics. Given the knowledge of the threat type and the associated thrust profile, we may be able to more easily deal with the problem.

This paper compares the performance of two traditional filtering techniques to a thrust profile based technique for tracking boosting targets. The paper compares the traditional (nearly) constant velocity and acceleration Kalman filters to (nearly) constant velocity and acceleration filters that compensate the state prediction for gravity and thrust accelerations. The paper demonstrates the benefits of using acceleration compensation, particularly when the thrust acceleration profile is known.

II. BOOSTING TARGET KINEMATICS

The most critical aspect of designing a tracking filter is matching the state transition (prediction step) to the real target kinematics. For the problem of interest being investigated in this paper, the forces acting upon a target under boost are rocket thrust, gravity (including altitude-dependence, non-spherical earth effects, and the effects of coriolis and centripetal forces), and drag on the target. Because of the uncertainties of tracking in boost inclusion of forces beyond thrust and gravity typically do not contribute to a better estimate of the target state. Therefore the filter prediction step will consist of two components: a simple gravity model and a simple booster thrust model.

A simple model of booster thrust induced acceleration magnitude is given by the rocket equation [1]. The basic rocket equation for thrust derived acceleration is given as

$$a_t(t) = \frac{F_T}{m_0 + \dot{m}t}, \quad (1)$$

where F_T is the force of thrust, m_0 is the mass at launch, \dot{m} is the change in mass (usually the negative of the propellant flow rate), and t is the time of flight (or time since launch). The force of thrust can be determined as

$$F_T = \dot{m}I_{sp}, \quad (2)$$

where I_{sp} is the specific energy of the propellant (also accounting for the efficiency of the rocket assembly). The acceleration vector can, at a low to medium fidelity, be assumed to have a magnitude given above, and act in the direction aligned with the velocity vector. The force of gravity can be modeled simply as

$$g = g_0 \left(\frac{R_e}{R_e + A} \right)^2, \quad (3)$$

where g_0 is a gravitational constant at the earth's surface, R_e is the nominal radius of the earth, and A is the target altitude above the surface of the earth. The acceleration vector is assumed to have a magnitude given above, and whose direction points from the target to the center of the earth.

III. FILTERING METHODS

In the course of this investigation, we examine the performance of four methods of filtering a boosting target: the nearly constant velocity model, the nearly constant acceleration model, the nearly constant velocity model with acceleration compensation, and the nearly constant acceleration model with thrust compensation. All of the filters use the basic Kalman filter approach. The Kalman filter equations can be written as:

$$\mathbf{P}_{k+1|k} = \Phi \mathbf{P}_{k|k} \Phi^T + \mathbf{Q}_{k+1|k}, \quad (4)$$

$$\mathbf{K}_{k+1} = \mathbf{P}_{k+1|k} \mathbf{H}^T [\mathbf{H} \mathbf{P}_{k+1|k} \mathbf{H}^T + \mathbf{R}]^{-1}, \quad (5)$$

$$\mathbf{P}_{k+1|k+1} = (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{K}_{k+1} \mathbf{H}) \mathbf{P}_{k+1|k}, \quad (6)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k+1|k} = \Phi \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k|k}, \quad (7)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k+1|k+1} = \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k+1|k} + \mathbf{K}_{k+1} (z_{k+1} - \mathbf{H} \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k+1|k}), \quad (8)$$

where $\mathbf{P}_{k+1|k}$ is the covariance matrix of the state prediction, Φ is the state transition matrix, $\mathbf{P}_{k|k}$ is the covariance matrix of the previous filtered state, $\mathbf{Q}_{k+1|k}$ is the process noise matrix, \mathbf{K}_{k+1} is the Kalman gain, \mathbf{H} is the observation matrix, \mathbf{R} is the measurement variance, $\mathbf{P}_{k+1|k+1}$ is the covariance matrix of the filtered state, $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k+1|k}$ is the predicted state, $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k|k}$ is the previous filtered state, $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k+1|k+1}$ is the filtered state, and z_{k+1} is the measurement. The specific details of each of the four methods examined are given next. Note that for all discussions presented here, the equations will be provided in generic one-dimensional form. Actual implementation is done in three dimensions. The details depend on choice of implementation (e.g. Kalman filter, extended Kalman filter, aeolotropic filter, etc.) and how each defines implementation state vectors and what form measurements are incorporated.

A. Nearly Constant Velocity Filter

The nearly constant velocity (CV) filter is the standard filter found in almost any tracking or estimation text [2-5]. The state vector consists of the position and velocity. The state transition matrix (for each component i) is given as:

$$\Phi_i = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \tau \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (9)$$

and the process noise matrix (for each component i) is given as

$$\mathbf{Q}_i = q \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\tau^4}{4} & \frac{\tau^3}{2} \\ \frac{\tau^3}{2} & \tau^2 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (10)$$

where τ is the time step and q is the process noise value. The value of q represents the unmodeled acceleration acting on the target and is chosen to minimize a cost function representing the error in the target state [6].

B. Nearly Constant Acceleration Filter

The nearly constant acceleration (CA) filter is also found in many of the same texts as the CV filter [2-5]. The state vector is defined as the position, velocity, and acceleration. The state transition matrix (for each component) then is given as:

$$\Phi_i = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \tau & \frac{\tau^2}{2} \\ 0 & 1 & \tau \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (11)$$

and the process noise matrix (for each component i) is given as

$$\mathbf{Q}_i = q \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\tau^4}{4} & \frac{\tau^3}{2} & \frac{\tau^2}{2} \\ \frac{\tau^3}{2} & \tau^2 & \tau \\ \frac{\tau^2}{2} & \tau & 1 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (12)$$

The process noise again represents unmodeled acceleration; however, since acceleration is included in the state model, we anticipate that a lower value of process noise will be required than for the CV filter when minimizing the cost function.

C. Constant Velocity With Acceleration Compensation Filter

By accounting for the known accelerations acting on the target, the unmodeled portion of the acceleration can be reduced, in some cases, to even less than the constant acceleration filter. Because the two largest forces acting on a boosting target are thrust and gravity, we modify the state prediction step in the CV filter to include a compensation term:

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k+1|k} = \Phi \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k|k} + \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\tau^2}{2} \\ \tau \end{bmatrix} (\mathbf{a}_t(t) + \mathbf{a}_g(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k|k})), \quad (13)$$

where \mathbf{a}_t is the acceleration vector due to thrust and \mathbf{a}_g is the acceleration vector due to gravity. One of the difficulties to this approach is to properly estimate the time since launch t needed to calculate \mathbf{a}_t . The other detail is that the thrust acceleration vectors must be projected onto the estimated velocity vector and the gravity must be projected along the vector between the target and earth's center. The magnitude of these thrust acceleration was described in Section II with an alternative formulation provided in the next section. The magnitude of the gravitational acceleration vector was discussed in Section II.

Other than the acceleration compensation, the rest of the CV filter is unchanged. The affect of the use of acceleration compensation is reduced optimal process noise resulting in "less noisy" estimation.

D. Constant Acceleration With Acceleration Compensation Filter

Because the acceleration from thrust given in (1) is constantly changing, state prediction using acceleration estimate based on previous update can still lead to a bias or lag in the state estimate. To compensate for this increase in acceleration, we modify the state prediction step. If we manipulate (1) and (2) we can solve for the acceleration magnitude at a specific time given a *previous* acceleration estimate as

$$a_i(t+\tau) = \frac{a_i(t)}{1 + \tau \frac{a_i(t)}{I_{sp}}} \quad (14)$$

The thrust derived acceleration is calculated from the filter acceleration estimate, $\hat{\mathbf{a}}(t)$, as

$$a_i(t) = \left\| \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k+1|k}(t) - \mathbf{a}_g(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k|k}) \right\|, \quad (15)$$

and then the compensated acceleration estimate is calculated from (14) and (15) as

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k+1|k} = \phi(\tau) \left(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k+1|k} - \mathbf{a}_g(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k|k}) \right) + \mathbf{a}_g(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k|k}) \quad (16)$$

where

$$\phi(\tau) = \frac{1}{1 + \tau \frac{a_i(t)}{I_{sp}}} \quad (17)$$

This compensation term for each component i is then incorporated into the covariance equations by modifying the transition matrix to be

$$\Phi_i = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \tau & \frac{\tau^2}{2} \\ 0 & 1 & \tau \\ 0 & 0 & \phi(\tau) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (18)$$

The state equations are not adjusted by this term, since the compensation is performed directly in (14) through (16).

IV. RESULTS

We evaluated the performance of the different filter types using a simulation consisting of a basic point mass model of a generic short range ballistic missile, a simple radar model that added Gaussian measurement noise to range, bearing, and elevation measurements, and the filters under investigation. The simulation was run to determine the optimal value of the process noise, q , for each of the filter types based on minimizing the mean plus three standard deviations error in the filtered position at the end of boost ($t = 60$ s). The simulation was then executed with each filter for 1000 Monte-Carlo runs to produce our results.

For the constant velocity (CV) filter with $q = 450\text{m}^2/\text{s}^4$, the position error is shown in Figure 1. The position error for the constant acceleration (CA) filter for $q = 0.6\text{m}^2/\text{s}^4$ is shown in Figure 2. The results of the CV filter with acceleration compensation with $q = 55\text{m}^2/\text{s}^4$ and the CA filter with acceleration compensation with $q = 0.067\text{m}^2/\text{s}^4$ are shown in Figure 3 and Figure 4, respectively.

We can gain some insight into the filter performance by simply examining the process noise values required for optimal performance. In both the constant velocity and constant acceleration cases, the addition of the acceleration compensation allowed us to reduce the process noise by an

order of magnitude. Physically, this means that the filters are able to better model the target kinematics. The position errors are reduced with the addition of acceleration compensation. Figures 5-8 show the velocity errors for the four filters from the same runs. Again, we see a reduction in the error with the addition of acceleration compensation.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The evaluation of these filter variations demonstrate that against a boosting target, the CA filter performs slightly better than the CV filter. The results for CV w/AC and CA w/AC filters demonstrate that acceleration compensation can be effective in improving tracking accuracy.

Further investigation is necessary into the selection of the correct threat's thrust profile for acceleration compensation (threat typing) and in the filter ability to handle transitions during staging events for multiple stage threats and transitions from boost phase to midcourse phase.

VI. REFERENCES

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Figure 1. Position Error for CV Filter

Figure 3. Position Error for CV/AC Filter

Figure 2. Position Error for CA Filter

Figure 4. Position Error for CA/AC Filter

Figure 5. Velocity Error for CV Filter

Figure 7. Velocity Error for CV/AC Filter

Figure 6. Velocity Error for CA Filter

Figure 8. Velocity Error for CA/AC Filter